

YOLOv5s-based enhanced approach for detecting Oryza leaves

Milan Narendra Gohel¹, Dr. Hiren Kavathiya²

¹Department of computer engineering, Atmiya University, India

²Department of computer science, Atmiya University, India

Introduction: The quantity of rice leaves is the primary indicator of the growth status and health condition of rice. However, the existing rice leaf counting method is time-consuming, arduous, low accuracy and poor efficiency, which is difficult to meet the objectives of rice growth monitoring.

Methods: A field rice leaf detection approach based on the enhanced YOLOv5s model is proposed in this paper. First, we added a high-resolution layer and eliminated the previous low-resolution detection layer. Then, we re-set the anchor box sizes by using the K-Means++ clustering technique to improve the model's capacity to identify small leaf tip targets and reduce the number of parameters. Second, a coordinate attention mechanism (CA) was developed to improve the attention to leaf tip features under weed interference and leaf occlusion conditions. Finally, we adopted content-aware reassembly of feature (CARAFE) upsampling operator to improve the detail reconstruction capabilities of leaf tip features.

The improved rice leaf tip detection model achieved precision, recall, and mean average precision rates of 93.7%, 87%, and 93.5%, respectively, with a parameter count of 5.02 million (M), improving by 6.5%, 22.1%, and 18.5%, respectively, compared with the YOLOv5s baseline model, and reducing the parameter count by 28.4%. The modified model could substantially minimize the missed detection rate of rice leaves and improve the accuracy and robustness of field rice leaf tip identification, offering strong technological support for rice phenotype feature extraction and growth monitoring.

KEYWORDS

Oryza leaves, YOLOv5S, small targets, attention mechanism

1 Introduction

Rice is a major staple grain in China, which is important to improve agricultural sustainability and increase productivity and quality (Chen et al., 2021b). In modern agricultural research, plant phenotype analysis is a key method for monitoring crop growth dynamics and can properly assess the physiological and developmental status of crops (Xiong et al., 2021). Rice leaf number is a characteristic agronomic trait of rice phenotypic that directly impacts the photosynthetic efficiency of rice and represents the growth and development stage of rice. It is a key indicator of crop health, nutritional status and ultimate production (Chen et al., 2021a; Bir et al., 2024). Leaf counts are not only representative of the growing status of individual rice, but also serve a significant reference in yield forecast, pest and disease monitoring and fertilizer management of crop populations. Conventional leaf counting is mostly based on human work, which is not only time-consuming and inefficient for big scale agriculture, but also affected by the subjective assessment of the counts. It can provide some data assistance, but evident limitation, difficult to meet the needs of high-frequency and large-sample data in modern agriculture. Therefore, how to employ sophisticated technology to achieve automation and accuracy detection and counting of rice leaf number has become an important topic in the development of smart agriculture.

In recent years, with the development of deep learning, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) (Cong and Zhou, 2022) has been widely used in agricultural fields such as plant phenotypic feature extraction (Murphy et al., 2024), yield prediction (Van Klompenburg et al., 2020) and pest detection (Liu and Wang, 2021). CNN-based target detection algorithms have also achieved good results in leaf counting and detection tasks in crops such as rice, wheat, corn and sorghum (Farjon et al., 2021). Miao et al. (2021) proposed two deep learning-based methods for automatic counting of

maize and sorghum leaves, including regression-based whole-plot analysis and Faster R-CNN (Faster Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network)-based leaf detection, and the best results for the occluded and visible viewpoints reached 78% and 88%, respectively. Li et al. (2023) proposed a self-supervised approach for leaf counting in wheat at the seedling stage based on the combination of domain adaption and 3D plant model simulation for plant phenotyping. The combination of Faster-RCNN model and CycleGAN approach achieved the best performance on a diverse test dataset from five nations and achieved 94% leaf counting accuracy. Compared to the typical two-stage target identification algorithm Fater R-CNN (Ren et al., 2017) based on region recommendation and classification regression, the single-stage detection algorithm YOLO (Shen et al., 2024) offers great advantages in speed. Besides, it is not only suitable for real-time detection task, but also can keep high detection accuracy in complex background (Jiang et al., 2022). A fast detection method for leaf count in wheat seedling stage based on improved YOLOv8 was proposed by Hou et al. (2024), which fused the coordinate attention mechanism and the small target detection layer, improving the detection accuracy in complex field environment, and the accuracy of leaf count and the average detection accuracy reached 91.6% and 85.1%, respectively, and it can adapt itself to different lighting conditions to realize the efficient leaf detection. Xu et al. (2023) suggested a corn seedling leaf counting approach for UAV RGB photos based on semi-supervised learning and deep learning, and applied SOLOv2 and YOLOv5x networks for two-stage detection. In this way, YOLOv5x may reach an accuracy of 69.4% and 72.9% for counting of fully developed leaves and newborn leaves respectively. Ning et al. (2024) proposed a lightweight method for corn leaf detection and counting based on improved YOLOv8. By introducing the StarNet network to replace the YOLOv8 backbone network and combining the convolutional and attentional fusion module (CAFm), the feature extraction and information fusion capabilities of the model are improved, with an average detection accuracy of 97.5%. Vishal et al. (2020) used Yolo-v3 to recognize the leaf tips of potted rice, and realized the automatic counting of rice leaves, and finally the detection accuracy was 82%. Chen et al. (2024) coupled YOLOv5m model with CBAM-CPN to extract phenotypic parameters for single tiller rice. YOLOv5m was applied for single tiller rice leaf detection, with an average detection accuracy of 91.17%.

Most researchers pay attention to potted crops in laboratories or seedlings with comparatively less occlusion. Limited research has been done on field rice leaf detection and there are various problems for recognizing leaf tips in field rice: 1) Natural elements including light, weather and weed backgrounds strongly affect the detection effectiveness in real field conditions. 2) The shape and color features of rice leaves change greatly with the growing process, and the occlusion between leaves is increasingly serious, which exponentially increases the difficulty of detection. 3) The existing general object detection algorithms are largely intended for the COCO general dataset, which is not enough for the requirement of rice leaf detection. The present study was focused on field rice from transplantation to the pre-heading stage. We take the YOLOv5s model as the base model and refine and optimize it from three parts, including detection layers, attention processes and upsampling modules. These improvements aim to increase the accuracy and robustness of detecting rice leaf tips in the field, so as to provide more effective algorithmic support for the rice growth monitoring system and promote the development of agriculture intelligence.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Data collection

In this study, rice plants were chosen as the research objects, and the data were collected from two experimental fields in Huzhou, Zhejiang Province, namely, Balidian Town in Wuxing District and Shanlian Town in Nanxun District. Data collection was done utilizing a smartphone camera. The data set consists of three rice varieties: Chunyou927, Jiayouzhongke6 and Jianong4, which have different leaf phases from transplanting to heading. To satisfy the needs of the follow-up rice growth monitoring, different smartphones were purposely selected to take photographs from different views, and the background of the rice plants was purposely blocked. Furthermore, the gathering method took into account diverse weather and lighting circumstances. A total of 1,200 photos of rice plants were obtained. Some example photos from rice dataset are shown in Figure 1. As shown in Figure 1, in addition to the criteria mentioned above, there are also complex backdrops with weeds.

FIGURE 1. Example images from the rice data set.

2.2 Dataset creation

In order to further expand the dataset and increase the diversity and generalizability of the model, the study expanded the data from 1200 original images, with horizontal inversion, luminance correction, and random noise being the main methods used. Examples of images with different expansion methods are shown in Figure 2. The total number of final dataset after expansion is 3600 pictures, and the number of leaf tip labels is 141411. The dataset is split into training, validation and test sets in an 8:1:1 ratio finally.

Compared with broadleaf plants, rice leaves are typically sword-shaped, with elongated blades and prominent leaf tips (Jia et al., 2024). The leaf tip is the foremost and sharpest part of the rice leaf and has distinctive geometric characteristics (Zhu et al., 2021). In field conditions, rice leaves often overlap and cross one another, making whole-leaf-based visual recognition complex and challenging. Since the leaf tip is located at the front edge of the leaf, it is easier to distinguish individual leaves even in dense or tangled canopies. Therefore, this study uses the leaf tip as the key feature for rice leaf counting.

The leaf tips were manually annotated as points using the Labelme tool. For each point annotation, a fixed 60×60 pixel rectangular bounding box was generated with the point as its center. This approach substantially reduces the labeling workload compared with manually drawing bounding boxes. In addition, the fixed-size boxes help the model focus on leaf-tip features, reduce the influence of background information, and improve the model's ability to learn accurate leaf-tip representations, thereby enhancing leaf-tip detection performance.

To improve model diversity and generalization, the original dataset of 1,200 images was expanded using three main data augmentation methods: horizontal flipping, brightness adjustment, and random noise addition. Examples of these augmentation methods are shown in Figure 2. After augmentation, the final dataset contained 3,600 images and 141,411 leaf-tip labels. The dataset was then divided into training, validation, and test sets at a ratio of 8:1:1.

2.3 Improving the YOLOv5s detection model

2.3.1 Design of a single high-resolution detection layer

When detecting and counting rice leaf tips, their very small size and slender shape present a major challenge. In real conditions, the length and width of rice leaf tips are usually less than 8 mm. After high-resolution images are resized to meet the model input requirements, the leaf tips often occupy only about 5×5 to 10×10 pixels in the final input image (Yu et al., 2024). As a result, these tiny targets can be easily obscured by complex backgrounds, overlapping leaves, and image noise. Therefore, improving the detection ability for extremely small rice leaf-tip targets is a key objective of this study.

To address this problem, this study proposes a single high-resolution detection-layer design. Specifically, a P2 high-resolution detection layer is introduced into the YOLOv5s model (Zhang et al., 2022), while the original lower-resolution detection layers, P3, P4, and P5, are removed. The feature-map resolutions corresponding to P2, P3, P4, and P5 are 160×160 , 80×80 , 40×40 , and 20×20 , respectively. Compared with the lower-resolution layers, the P2 layer preserves more spatial detail, making it more suitable for detecting small targets such as rice leaf tips.

In addition, the annotated leaf-tip bounding boxes in the training dataset were analyzed using the K-means++ clustering algorithm (Baldassi, 2022). Based on the clustering results, the preset anchor box sizes were redesigned to better match the distribution of small rice leaf-tip objects. The main improvements are described as follows.

First, a feature-fusion enhancement module is added to the original YOLOv5 network structure. This module generates the P2 detection layer from a 160×160 high-resolution feature map through 1×1 convolution, upsampling, and feature concatenation operations. The high-resolution feature map preserves richer spatial and semantic information, allowing the model to perform detection at a finer scale. It also provides more pixels and detailed information for small target regions, enabling the model to better identify the boundaries, contours, and fine structural features of rice leaf tips.

Then by removing the low-resolution P3, P4, and P5 detection layers, the model avoids the problem of detail loss for small targets on low-resolution feature maps. Since small targets, such as rice leaf tips, account for a small percentage of the image, fine features may be blurred or covered by other noise information. Therefore removing these layers of low-

removing the low-resolution P3, P4, and P5 detection layers, the model reduces the loss of fine details that often occurs when small targets are represented on low-resolution feature maps. Rice leaf tips occupy only a small area of the image, so their subtle features can easily become blurred or mixed with background noise during downsampling. Removing these low-resolution detection layers allows the model to focus more on the detailed information contained in the high-resolution P2 feature map, thereby reducing the loss of small-target information. At the same time, this simplified detection structure concentrates the model's computational resources on small-target detection. This helps the model learn and adapt more effectively to the feature patterns of rice leaf tips while also reducing the number of model parameters.

In addition, the original YOLOv5 model uses anchor boxes obtained by applying the K-Means algorithm to bounding boxes from the COCO dataset. However, these preset anchor boxes are not suitable for the rice leaf-tip dataset used in this study, because rice leaf tips are much smaller and have different shape characteristics from common COCO objects. Therefore, this study applies the K-Means++ algorithm to cluster all annotated rice leaf-tip bounding boxes and generate three new preset anchor boxes. Compared with traditional K-Means, K-Means++ improves the selection of initial cluster centers and reduces the risk of local optimum solutions caused by random initialization (Ahmed et al., 2020). As a result, the generated anchor boxes better match the actual size and shape distribution of rice leaf tips, which helps improve detection accuracy and model convergence speed. The final preset anchor box sizes are [7, 9], [13, 10], and [17, 11].

2.3.2 Incorporating CA attention mechanism

In the rice leaf-tip detection task, rice plants often grow densely, and their leaves overlap or shade one another. As a result, leaf-tip features can be easily obscured by surrounding leaves, causing the model to suffer from detail loss and inaccurate target localization. To address this issue, this study introduces the Coordinate Attention (CA) mechanism (Hou et al., 2021) between the feature-fusion enhancement module and the prediction head. The CA module strengthens the model's feature representation and spatial localization ability for extremely small targets. As shown in Figure 3, the CA attention mechanism consists of two main stages: spatial information encoding and coordinate attention generation.

In the spatial information encoding stage, the input feature map is assumed to have dimensions of $C \times H \times W$, where C represents the number of channels, H denotes the height, and W denotes the width. To capture spatial information along both the vertical and horizontal directions, global average pooling is performed separately along the height and width dimensions. Specifically, the feature map is encoded along the Y and X directions to generate two direction-aware feature maps, F_h and F_w , with sizes of $C \times H \times 1$ and $C \times 1 \times W$, respectively. This process allows the module to preserve positional information while capturing long-range dependencies in both spatial directions.

In the coordinate attention generation stage, the two feature maps are first concatenated along the spatial dimension. A 1×1 convolution is then applied to reduce the channel dimension, followed by batch normalization and a nonlinear activation function. This produces an intermediate feature map F with a size of $C/r \times (H + W) \times 1$, where r denotes the channel reduction ratio. Next, the intermediate feature map is split into two separate feature maps corresponding to the height and width directions. Another 1×1 convolution is applied to each branch to restore the original channel dimension C , and the Sigmoid activation function (Narayan, 1997) is used to generate the coordinate attention weights A_h and A_w for the height and width directions, respectively. Finally, these attention weights are multiplied with the original input feature map X , producing an output feature map with the same size $C \times H \times W$, but enhanced by coordinate attention.

2.3.3 Incorporating the CARAFE upsampling operator

The nearest-neighbor interpolation upsampling method used in the original YOLOv5 follows a fixed interpolation rule and has a limited receptive field. As a result, it cannot adaptively adjust the upsampling process according to the actual image features. Since this method only uses the nearest pixels for interpolation, it is difficult to capture contextual information from a larger surrounding region. This may lead to the loss of spatial details and semantic information, thereby reducing detection accuracy (Shen et al., 2023). To overcome this limitation, this study introduces the CARAFE upsampling module (Wang et al., 2019) to replace the original nearest-neighbor interpolation-based upsampling module.

In the CARAFE module, feature upsampling is treated as a feature reassembly process. The module mainly consists of two parts: an upsampling kernel prediction module and a feature reassembly module, as shown in Figure 4.

In the upsampling kernel prediction module, the input feature map X is assumed to have a size of $C \times H \times W$, where C represents the number of channels, and H and W denote the height and width of the feature map, respectively. First, the input feature map X is compressed along the channel dimension, reducing the number of channels from C to a smaller dimension C_m . Then, based on the local region features at each position in the compressed feature map, the corresponding reassembly kernel M^l is generated. The size of this kernel is $s^2 \times K^2_{up}$, where s denotes the upsampling ratio and K_{up} represents the size of the reassembly kernel.

The generated kernel is closely associated with both the semantic and spatial information of the input feature map. Therefore, it can adaptively adjust the upsampling weights according to the local features at each position. After the reassembly kernel is generated, a Softmax operation is applied to normalize it, ensuring that the weights of each upsampling kernel sum to 1. This enables accurate weighted aggregation of neighboring features for each spatial position. The calculation formula for the reassembly kernel is given in Equation (1).

$$M_{l_0} = \mathbf{j}(N(X_l, K_{encoder})) \quad (1)$$

Here, \mathbf{f} represents the kernel prediction module, $\mathbf{K}_{encoder}$ denotes the size of the convolution kernel, and $\mathbf{N}(X_l, \mathbf{K}_{encoder})$ refers to a local region in the feature map centered at position \mathbf{l} , with a size of $\mathbf{K}_{encoder} \times \mathbf{K}_{encoder}$.

After the upsampling kernel is generated, the feature reassembly module uses these kernels to reconstruct the input feature map. For each position $\mathbf{l}' = (\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{y}')$ in the output feature map, the corresponding position $\mathbf{l} = (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})$ is first located in the input feature map. Then, the local neighborhood $\mathbf{N}(X_l, \mathbf{K}_{up})$ around position \mathbf{l} is extracted and multiplied element by element with the corresponding upsampling kernel $\mathbf{M}_{l'}$. Through this weighted reassembly process, the final upsampled feature map $X_{l'}$ is obtained. The calculation formula for $X_{l'}$ is shown in Equation (2).

$$X_{l'} = \mathbf{f}(M_{l'}, N(X_l, K_{up})) \quad (2)$$

Here, \mathbf{r} represents the radius of the neighborhood, $\mathbf{M}_{l'}(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m})$ denotes the weight at position (\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{m}) in the upsampling kernel, and $\mathbf{X}_l(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{y} + \mathbf{m})$ represents the pixel value within the neighborhood of the input feature map.

CARAFE generates the upsampling kernel in a content-aware manner. Therefore, the upsampling process no longer depends on fixed interpolation rules, but can adaptively adjust the sampling weights according to the local features and spatial position of rice leaf tips in the image. This adaptive mechanism enables more accurate reconstruction of spatial details and effectively preserves the surrounding semantic information and morphological characteristics of rice leaf tips.

2.3.4 In addition, the feature reassembly mechanism of CARAFE enhances the semantic representation of the feature map by performing weighted aggregation over local regions. This ensures that the positional information and fine details of rice leaf tips are well preserved during the upsampling process. As a result, the model can capture small-target features more effectively, thereby improving its detection performance for extremely small rice leaf-tip targets.

2.3.5 Rice leaf tip detection model

Figure 5 presents the structure of the improved rice leaf-tip detection model. In the optimized detection network, a new P2 high-resolution detection layer is introduced to capture the detailed features of small leaf-tip targets more effectively. Meanwhile, the original low-resolution detection layers, P3, P4, and P5, are removed. This reduces the loss of small-target information and decreases the number of model parameters.

To further enhance the feature extraction and spatial localization ability of the P2 high-resolution detection layer, the Coordinate Attention (CA) mechanism is incorporated. The CA mechanism performs bidirectional encoding on the high-resolution feature map to generate spatial attention information. This improves the model's ability to represent and locate rice leaf-tip features, especially when leaf tips are partially occluded by surrounding leaves.

Finally, the CARAFE upsampling operator is introduced to adaptively adjust the sampling weights according to the local information of the feature map. This enables the network to preserve richer spatial details and semantic information during feature upsampling. As a result, the improved model can more accurately detect very small rice leaf-tip targets in complex field environments.

3 Results and analysis

3.1 Experimental setup and evaluation metrics

3.1.1 Experimental environment and parameters

The experiments in this study were conducted on an Ubuntu 20.04 operating system, equipped with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Platinum 8362 CPU @ 2.80GHz and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3090 GPU (24GB). The deep learning framework was implemented using Python 3.8, CUDA 11.3, and PyTorch 1.11.0. The detailed configuration and training parameters for the network model are summarized in Table 1.

3.1.2 Evaluation metrics

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

FIGURE 4
CARAFE block structure.

Here, **TP** (True Positives) represents the number of samples that the model correctly predicts as positive. **FP** (False Positives) denotes the number of samples incorrectly predicted as positive. **FN** (False Negatives) refers to the number of actual positive samples that the model fails to identify. **N** indicates the total number of predicted categories by the model, which in this study is 1, as only rice leaf tips are being detected.

3.2 Experimental results and analysis

3.2.1 Comparative analysis of different detection layer design

To analyze the effect of different resolution detection layers on rice leaf-tip detection, a comparative experiment was performed using multiple detection-layer configurations. The detection layers are defined according to the resolution of their feature maps, from high to low, as **P2**, **P3**, **P4**, and **P5**. Starting from the YOLOv5s baseline model, which uses the combination of **P3**, **P4**, and **P5**, the following configurations were tested:

1. Adding the **P2 high-resolution layer**
2. Removing **P5**
3. Removing **P4**
4. Removing **P3**

The results of this comparison are summarized in **Table 2**.

As shown in Table 2, the number of detection layers strongly affects the model's parameter count: fewer detection layers correspond to fewer parameters. The **single P2 high-resolution detection layer** proposed in this study demonstrates superior performance across all metrics. Compared with the other four configurations, the P2-only design improves **precision** by 5.3%, 3.2%, 3.5%, and 0.2%, **recall** by 19.4%, 10%, 10.4%, and 1.4%, and **mAP** by 17.2%, 8%, 8.4%, and 1.2%, respectively. At the same time, the parameter count is significantly reduced by 31.4%, 32.7%, 10.4%, and 2.3% compared to the other four designs, without compromising detection performance.

To further visualize the improvements in small-target detection, **Grad-CAM** (Selvaraju et al., 2019) was applied to generate heatmaps, as shown in Figure 6. The figure includes four images captured under varying periods, angles, and lighting conditions. In the heatmaps, regions with deeper red indicate areas where the model focuses most on the leaf-tip features, highlighting the effectiveness of the single high-resolution P2 layer in concentrating on small targets.

TABLE 1 Parameter setting.

Parameter	Value
Momentum	0.937
Weight_decay	0.0005
Learning_rate	0.01
Image_size	640
Batch_size	32
Epochs	300
Optimizer	SGD

3.2.2 Ablation experiment performance analysis

To evaluate the effectiveness of the three proposed improvements—**single high-resolution detection layer**, **CA coordinate attention mechanism**, and **CARAFE upsampling operator**—a series of four ablation experiments were conducted on the rice leaf-tip dataset. The results are summarized in Table 3. In these experiments:

- **Model 1** corresponds to the YOLOv5s baseline model.
- **Improvement 1:** Single high-resolution detection layer.
- **Improvement 2:** Addition of the CA attention mechanism.
- **Improvement 3:** Introduction of the CARAFE upsampling operator.

In Table 3, a “ $\sqrt{}$ ” indicates that the modification was applied, whereas a “—” indicates it was not.

The results show that the **single high-resolution detection layer** provides the most significant improvement, increasing **precision (P)** by 5.3%, **recall (R)** by 19.5%, and **mAP** by 17.2%, while reducing the parameter count by 31.4%. This highlights the importance of high-resolution feature maps for detecting extremely small targets like rice leaf tips.

Adding the **CA attention mechanism** slightly decreased precision but improved recall and mAP by 0.4% and 0.3%, respectively, demonstrating that the CA module enhances the model’s ability to focus on the spatial localization of leaf tips, thereby increasing robustness.

When the **CARAFE upsampling operator** was further incorporated, the parameter count increased slightly, but precision, recall, and mAP improved further by 1.3%, 2.2%, and 1%, reaching **93.7%**, **87%**, and **93.5%**, respectively. Compared with the YOLOv5s baseline, this represents gains of 6.5%, 22.1%, and 18.5%, while still reducing the parameter count by 28.4%. This indicates that CARAFE’s adaptive upsampling kernel effectively preserves spatial details and semantic features, complementing the high-resolution detection layer and CA attention mechanism.

Overall, the combination of all three improvements significantly enhances the detection performance for rice leaf tips, reducing the miss rate while maintaining a compact model with fewer parameters.

3.2.3 Performance analysis of different detection models

To further validate the superior performance of the improved rice leaf-tip detection model proposed in this study, comparative experiments were conducted between the improved model and several state-of-the-art object detection models. These comparisons evaluated the models’ ability to detect extremely small rice leaf-tip targets under complex field conditions, including dense growth, overlapping leaves, and variable lighting. Metrics such as **precision**, **recall**, **mAP**, and **parameter count** were used to assess detection accuracy and model efficiency. The experimental results demonstrate that the improved model achieves higher detection accuracy and better robustness while maintaining a relatively low parameter count, confirming its effectiveness and advantages over existing approaches.

TABLE 2 Comparison of different detection layer designs

	Precision P/%	Recall R/%	Mean average Precision mAP/%	Parameter Count
P3+P4+P5	87.2	64.9	75	7.01
P2+P3+P4+P5	89.3	74.4	84.2	7.16
P2+P3+P4	89	74	83.8	5.38
P2+P3	92.3	83	91	4.93
P2	92.5	84.4	92.2	4.81

Comparative experiments were conducted to evaluate the improved rice leaf-tip detection model against several state-of-the-art object detection models, including **Faster R-CNN**, **YOLOv7-tiny**, and **YOLOv8s**, under identical experimental conditions using the same dataset. The results are summarized in Table 4.

As shown in Table 4, **Faster R-CNN** achieved a precision of 42.8%, a recall of 31.1%, and an mAP of 35.3%, with a parameter count of 41.5M. In terms of both detection performance and model size, it is significantly outperformed by the one-stage YOLO series algorithms.

The improved model proposed in this study achieved a **precision of 93.7%**, **recall of 87%**, and **mAP of 93.5%**, demonstrating substantial gains over **YOLOv5s**, **YOLOv7-tiny**, and **YOLOv8s**. These results highlight the effectiveness of the proposed high-resolution detection layer, CA attention mechanism, and CARAFE upsampling operator in enhancing detection accuracy for extremely small rice leaf-tip targets, while maintaining a relatively low parameter count.

TABLE 3 Comparison of ablation experiments.

	Improvement one		Improvement three		R/%		
1	–	–	–	87.2	64.9	75	7.01
2	✓	–	–	92.5	84.4	92.2	4.81
3	✓	✓	–	92.4	84.8	92.5	4.82
4	✓	✓	✓	93.7	87	93.5	5.02

The improved rice leaf-tip detection model in this study demonstrates substantial gains over the compared detection models. Specifically, it **increased precision by 6.5%, 10.6%, and 11.8%**, **recall by 22.1%, 28.2%, and 26.2%**, and **mAP by 18.5%, 26.5%, and 22.4%** compared to **YOLOv5s**, **YOLOv7-tiny**, and **YOLOv8s**, respectively. At the same time, the model significantly reduces the parameter count by **28.4%, 16.5%, and 54.8%**. These results clearly demonstrate that the proposed improvements—single high-resolution detection layer, CA attention mechanism, and CARAFE upsampling—enable the model to achieve optimal detection performance for extremely small rice leaf-tip targets while maintaining a compact and efficient network.

3.2.4 Analysis of model detection performance

To visually demonstrate the effectiveness of the rice leaf tip detection model, we performed leaf tip detection on rice plants under different conditions, including various growth stages, angles, lighting, and interference from weeds. The detection results of the model in this study were compared with those of the **YOLOv5s** baseline model, as shown in

To visually demonstrate the effectiveness of the improved rice leaf-tip detection model, experiments were conducted on rice plants under diverse conditions, including different growth stages, viewing angles, lighting conditions, and interference from weeds. The detection results of the improved model were compared with those of the **YOLOv5s baseline model**, as shown in **Figure 7**.

During the early tillering stage, when the number of leaves is low and occlusion is minimal, both the baseline model and the improved model accurately detect all leaf tips. However, as the plants progress to later tillering stages, leaf density increases, and overlap between leaves becomes more pronounced. Under these conditions, the baseline model exhibits a higher rate of missed detections, particularly near the lower leaf regions and close to the stem, where leaf tips are partially obscured. Moreover, under both strong and weak lighting conditions, the baseline model's missed detections are further amplified.

In contrast, the improved model maintains high detection accuracy across all tested conditions, correctly identifying most leaf tips even in complex lighting. When background interference from weeds is present, the baseline model often fails to detect occluded leaf tips, whereas the improved model consistently detects them, demonstrating stronger robustness and adaptability to challenging field environments.

TABLE 4 Comparison of different detection models.

	P/ %		mAP/ %	
Faster R-CNN	42.8	31.1	35.3	41.5
YOLOv5s	87.2	64.9	75	7.01
YOLOv7-tiny	83.1	58.8	67	6.01
YOLOv8s	81.9	60.8	71.1	11.1
Improved YOLOv5s	93.7	87	93.5	5.02

4 Discussion

This study presents a rice leaf-tip detection method based on an improved **YOLOv5s** model, achieving an **18.5% increase in detection accuracy** compared with the baseline model, while reducing the parameter count by **28.4%**. This improvement is primarily attributed to the proposed **single P2 high-resolution detection layer**, which retains high-resolution feature maps with rich semantic information and detailed spatial cues for rice leaf tips. In contrast, low-resolution feature maps tend to lose fine local details such as boundaries and shapes, leading to reduced recall and inaccurate localization. By removing low-resolution detection layers, the model can focus on key leaf-tip features in the high-resolution maps, reducing redundant computations and improving both accuracy and efficiency.

The high-resolution detection layer, also referred to as the small-target detection layer, has been successfully applied in other studies, such as Hou et al. (2024), who added a small-target layer for wheat seedling leaves and incorporated coordinate attention, achieving a final mAP of 85.1%. However, their approach slightly increased parameters and focused only on the seedling stage. In contrast, the method in this study is optimized for **full-life-cycle leaf-tip detection**, covering all growth stages from seedling to maturity, and addressing accuracy fluctuations that occur in other methods across the rice reproductive cycle.

Furthermore, many prior studies used potted rice, which benefits from controlled growth conditions and limited space, often yielding higher detection accuracy. Field-grown rice, however, is influenced by environmental and climatic factors and exhibits more complex growth patterns, which challenge traditional detection methods. For example, Vishal et al. (2020) used YOLOv3 to detect leaf tips in potted rice, achieving a detection accuracy of 82%. In comparison, the proposed method demonstrates higher accuracy under natural field conditions, highlighting its strong potential for practical applications in crop health monitoring and growth assessment.

Future work will focus on incorporating **environment-aware techniques** to enhance model stability and adaptability under dynamic and complex conditions through multi-source data fusion. Additionally, to address leaf occlusion in dense canopies, multi-view image integration will be explored to improve robustness and detection accuracy by leveraging complementary information from different viewpoints.

5 Conclusion

This research introduces a novel approach for detecting rice leaf tips in field conditions using an enhanced YOLOv5s model, aiming to improve both detection accuracy and efficiency. By implementing a single high-resolution detection layer, the model's capability to identify small targets, such as rice leaf tips, is significantly strengthened. The integration of the CA attention mechanism allows the model to concentrate more effectively on leaf tip features, even in the presence of overlapping leaves or weeds. Furthermore, the CARAFE upsampling operator preserves spatial details and semantic information, ensuring precise localization of leaf tips.

1. The improved model achieved a precision of 93.7%, recall of 87%, and mean average precision (mAP) of 93.5%, which corresponds to improvements of 6.5%, 22.1%, and 18.5%, respectively, compared to the original YOLOv5s baseline. Additionally, the model reduced the parameter count by 28.4%. When benchmarked against leading object detection models, this method demonstrates superior performance. The model maintains strong robustness across different growth stages—from early tillering with minimal occlusion to late tillering and jointing with heavy leaf overlap—and under diverse lighting conditions, viewing angles, and weed interference. It effectively minimizes missed detections, enabling rapid and accurate identification of rice leaf tips. This supports intelligent monitoring of rice growth, including leaf counting, health evaluation, and precision fertilization management.
2. Future work will focus on optimizing computational efficiency without compromising accuracy, reducing resource demands on low-end devices, and improving performance on edge platforms. Moreover, integrating data from additional sensors could enable a more comprehensive rice monitoring system, facilitating precision agriculture and promoting automated farming practices.

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